

A Discussion of Unconventional Theories related to Gravity: Energy, Plasmas and Propulsion

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Abstract

Gravitational theory has remained at an impasse for a great many years. Theoretical questions of substantial importance remain unanswered, such as: “Is there coupling of electromagnetic fields and gravitational fields?” This paper will reveal the reasons for the evident difficulty in theoretical advancement and begin to point the way toward needed corrections of gravitational theory with an emphasis placed upon actual experimental results and practical solutions. These recommendations and analyses may in turn allow quick realization of the many benefits now concealed beneath current accepted theory, which include but are not limited to: 1. clean, inexpensive, near limitless energy for industry and the populous, and 2. practical means of utilizing mass as a variable potentially including, industrial applications, space and terrestrial travel. The possible validity of Einstein’s Twin Paradox and a conditional solution implying a mechanism of absolute time are discussed. New gravitational theory is proposed. Specific gravity based designs demonstrating over one efficiency are proposed for experimental and practical testing, confirmation and subsequent duplication. Once the private sector and those associated scientific resources are applied toward correction and directed application of gravitational theory in the context of electrical and magnetic effects, one can speak of a new age. *Gravity*.

Keywords: Gravitational theory, Einstein’s Twin Paradox, New gravitational theory, Electromagnetic fields, Gravitational fields.

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1. Introduction

Gravitational theory contains within its hidden mysteries the solutions to the troubles of mankind. From clean energy and resultant human monetary independence to space travel, the wellspring of human hope and knowledge runs toward knowledge of gravity and its mechanisms. However, we see no real progress and also, false theories are placed before the public and academia as facts [1-3].

Current gravitational theory is mainly based in the work of Einstein. However, there are problems with standard relativistic and gravitational science. From van Flandern's seminal essay *Gravity, What the Experiments Say* [4] the following points are brought forward²:

- Why do photons from the Sun travel in directions not parallel to the direction of Earth's gravitational acceleration toward the Sun?
- Why do total eclipses of the Sun by the Moon reach maximum eclipse about 40 seconds before the Sun and Moon's gravitational forces align?
- How do binary pulsars anticipate each other's future position, velocity, and acceleration faster than the light time between them would allow?
- How can black holes have gravity when nothing can escape because the escape speed is greater than the speed of light?

Also, there is the question of causality involving static field dynamics. [4, 6]

Gravitational lensing and red shift can be explained without recourse to theory involving paradoxical notions. One can explain it with refraction (and atmospheric interactivity) as in: [4, 7-9]. Remembering the basic relation between a foundational Special Relativity and dependent General Relativity, note the following from the above reference [10]:

“(...) special relativity is nowhere exactly valid in the universe at large, because at cosmological distances the universe is a medium with high energy density (since it is everywhere filled up with light or stars), and

the space within galaxies is a notorious physical medium filled up of gases, particles and dust.” [10]

Recall that Special Relativity was conceived within particular conditions of constraint: the speed of light is a fixed value c **only** as it propagates *in a vacuum*.

From, [9]

“General Relativity predicts no diffraction with gravitational lensing since gravity warped space-time should bend all wavelengths equally. General Relativity theorists suggests the lack of diffraction in lensing is evidence their theory is correct. Yet “Einstein Rings” are blue. . . . The blue color is an indication of diffraction.” [9]

Also from the same source:

“If refraction is the actual cause of lensing, a major assumption driving the dark matter search would be swept away. Because of such assumptions, critics suggest that even after decades of searching, dark matter remains dark — because it does not exist.”

Indeed, this is our view as well³.

Recall that General Relativity, is in fact, based all but entirely upon (minimization of) time dilation. Is Bernard Burchell correct in his startling conclusion which states: “The acceleration time dilation aspects of General Relativity (GR) are internally self-contradictory and thus could not be true.” [13] He may well be. We suggest that there are alternatives which can provide scientifically useful systems of calculation and analysis, and those systems are free from relativistic paradox. [3] The subject of cogent alternative gravitational theories in general is too broad in scope to be covered within this document. We note that the alternate gravitational theory of Santilli known as Iso-Gravitation may be found explained generally and placed historically within reference [3] and then, covered in deep mathematical detail within the references specified therein.

2. History of Gravitational Theory and Basis of Field Effects.

Van Flandern states:

“The most amazing thing I was taught as a

² See also [5].

³ See also [11, 12].

graduate student of celestial mechanics at Yale in the 1960s was that all gravitational interactions between bodies in all dynamical systems had to be taken as instantaneous. Yet, anyone with a computer and orbit computation or numerical integration software can verify the consequences of introducing a delay into gravitational interactions. The effect on computed orbits is usually disastrous because conservation of angular momentum is destroyed." [4]

If celestial mechanics requires proper superluminal gravitational propagation speeds, Einstein's Relativity must be incorrect in terms of hypothesizing gravitational propagation at c , so why is current gravitational theory muddled in falsehood? Is there a reason the facts are hidden? Is there history and other thinking revealing proper theory?

From: Project Winterhaven: A Proposal for Joint Services Research and Development Contract; T. Brown, 1952 [14], reads:

"In the dusty unpublished notes of Sir Oliver Heaviside, written in the latter part of the nineteenth century, a remarkably adequate theory of gravitation was proposed. ... Brown developed the thesis that, due to the similar or equivalent nature of the electric and gravitational fields, a reciprocal influence could be expected which, if constrained, would give rise to physical forces detectable under certain circumstances (...) In recent years, as additional data of a confirming nature became available, the research has been associated with government research projects of a highly classified status, and publication has been precluded."

From Electrogravitics Systems Reports on a New Propulsion Methodology, edited by Thomas Valone [15], reads:

"The basic research and technology behind electro-anti-gravitation is so much in its infancy that this is perhaps one field of development where not only the methods but the ideas are secret. Nothing therefore can be discussed freely at the moment." [15]

The preceding quote is from 1954.

It may be inferred, therefore, that proper gravitational theory has been developed and actively suppressed so as to serve covert military purposes. The private sector must begin to utilize this science.

The history of functional gravitational theory

and its related basic causal dynamics are defined within [16] and [17] and that work [18] is also key. Also, we will discuss briefly the vital work of Thornhill [19] and the electromagnetic aetherial triality which is emergent from the interactions of the energy density (that is the aetherial substrate) and the electromagnetic waves it supports.

First we will examine the vital text [17] by E. T. Whittaker: "On the partial differential equations of mathematical physics". Within this little known yet deeply insightful piece of mathematical analysis which sought the solution of Laplace's potential equation and of the general differential equation of wave motions as well as of other equations derived from them, we see the introduction of electromagnetic field and electromagnetic wave associated longitudinal expressions which are not bound by the same propagational speed restrictions, but may well approach instantaneous propagation speeds. At the bottom of page 354 of reference [17] reads that

"The total disturbance at any point, due to this system of waves, is therefore independent of the time, and is everywhere proportional to the gravitational potential due to the particle at the point"

while on page 355 reads

"... To each of these terms will correspond one of the constituent fields. In each of these constituent fields the potential will be constant along each wave-front, and consequently the gravitational force in each constituent field will be perpendicular to the wave-front, *i.e. the waves will be longitudinal.*

But these results assimilate the propagation of gravity to that of light: for the undulatory phenomena just described, in which the varying vector is a gravitational force perpendicular to the wave-front, may be compared with the undulatory phenomena made familiar by the electromagnetic theory of light, in which the varying vectors consist of electric and magnetic forces parallel to the wave-front. The waves are in other respects exactly similar, and it seems probable that an identical property of the medium ensures their transmission through space.

This undulatory theory of gravity would require that gravity should be propagated with a finite velocity, which however need not be the same as that of light, and may be enormously greater." [17]

It appears that the waves' medium, the electrical energy density or aether as it was known, permits longitudinal gravitational wave propagation speeds independent of time. This same aether, or undifferentiated potential energy density then, supports propagation at c for electromagnetic expressions and propagation speeds well over c for those longitudinal waves which support gravitation.

We will take note quickly of the other important paper, [16] by E. T. Whittaker, "On an Expression of the Electromagnetic Field Due to Electrons by Means of Two Scalar Potential Functions." Within this work, we see that all of the facets of manifest electromagnetic field expressions themselves may be derived from just two scalar potentials! [^]

Then, by way of experiment, it may be seen that those electromagnetic potentials which are the mathematical causal foundation of electromagnetic effects are not mere mathematical abstractions, but actual physical objects as they must be within quantum theory, objects which in and of themselves have physical effects. [18]

It is deduced:

The basis for field effects in general, inclusive of the gravitational field and electromagnetic fields and their independent velocities of propagation can then be seen to be based in the scalar potential field, and it is proposed that scalar potential field is itself simply the organizational potential of the aetherial energy density.

Next, much may be learnt about the longitudinal component of electromagnetic expression and correct the errors of current theory through study of Thornhill's triality [19] as manifest within a proper model which includes the medium through which waves travel, the energy density which was once called aether.

Thornhill (1984) [19] may be understood and the error corrected by reintroducing the propagational medium (aether/energy-density) to the physics and using the correct Total Time Derivative to then be applied in calculations specifying the medium's system dynamics as *bound to mass*, and so implying a return to a partial time derivative in the medium's unbound stationary state.

From Thornhill (1984) [19], it is seen that:

For general unsteady motion of a gas in three space- variables x_i , ($i = 1, 2, 3$) when the fluid velocity components are denoted by u_i , the governing equations may be written, again using the summation convention,

$$\text{(Mass)} \quad \frac{Dv}{Dt} - \frac{v\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} = -Av^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{(Momentum)} \quad \frac{Du_i}{Dt} + \frac{v\partial p}{\partial x_i} = B_i v \quad (2)$$

$$\text{(Energy)} \quad \frac{DS}{Dt} = v(H - Apv)/T \quad (3)$$

Here p denotes, pressure, v specific volume, S specific entropy, T absolute temperature and the total time-derivative, moving with the fluid, is given by

$$\frac{D}{Dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + u_i \partial / \partial x_i \quad (4)$$

In the assembly of Maxwell's equations, the time-derivatives which occur in Ampère's rule and in the laws of induction have invariably been interpreted as the partial derivative $\partial/\partial t$. This is not acceptable in the concept of a gas-like ethereal medium, where the ethereal velocity may vary from point to point and with time, and the Newtonian frame of reference may be chosen so that its origin moves at any constant speed, independent of the ethereal motion. To satisfy the requirements of a gas-like ether unambiguously, the time-derivative in Ampère's rule and the laws of induction can only be interpreted as the total time-derivative moving with the ethereal flow, namely D/Dt , as defined in Eq. (4) above.

[^] Recent analysis implies a slight correction to the paper [16] cited, see: *Hadronic Journal*, C. K. Whitney, Generalized functions in relativistic potential theory. vol 10, 1987, p. 289-290. and; T. Bearden, *Gravitobiology*, 1991, Cheniere press. p. 76. 4 such potentials are sometimes needed to replace classical EM with scalar interferometry in consideration of torqueing in multi-bodied systems.

Note that the above referenced work [19] (Thornhill, 1984) brings forward not only the information concerning the total time derivative but also the important fact that oscillations within the medium form longitudinal condensations along a transverse wave front. These ideas are brought out best by studying the original paper in detail but, basically, Thornhill points out that, in a gas-like aether, the duality between the oscillating electric and magnetic fields, which are transverse to the direction of propagation of electromagnetic waves, becomes a triality with the longitudinal oscillations of motion of the aether, if electric field, magnetic field and motion are coexistent and mutually perpendicular. He points out that, therefore, it must be shown that, if electromagnetic waves comprise also longitudinal condensational oscillations of a gas-like aether, analogous to sound waves in a material gas, then all three aspects of such waves must propagate together along identical wave fronts. To this end, the full characteristic hyperconoids must be derived for the equations governing the motion and the electric and magnetic field-strengths in a gas-like aether in three space variables and time. All that is required is achieved in the cited article.

Also, the reader should note that in adjusting the total time derivative to account for a *bound* condition, where the medium moves with associated mass, a physical basis for charge itself follows, as the aether/energy density is itself bound to the matter with which it is associated. Charge may now be given a sensible physical basis as mobile aethereal expressions bound to molecular motion as a moving medium.

This correction and specification then allows for the correction of a piece of vital physics, *presented within CIA released documents as closely associated with Tesla*, that has finally been revealed, although with flaws, from behind the cloak of state secrecy: a new solution to the equations of Maxwell allowing the representation and derivation of scalar wave phenomenon. Referring to the relevant equations in the released CIA document [20] “CIA-RDP96-00792R000500240001-6”⁴,

it follows that with

$$\bar{E} = -\nabla\phi - \frac{1}{c} \frac{D\bar{A}}{Dt} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\bar{B} = \nabla \times \bar{A}, \quad (6)$$

where ϕ is the scalar (electric) potential and \bar{A} is the vector (magnetic) potential.

The modified Maxwell equations then predict

$$\nabla^2\phi - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{D^2\phi}{Dt^2} = 0 \quad (7)$$

and

$$\nabla^2\bar{A} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{D^2\bar{A}}{Dt^2} = 0 \quad (8)$$

As pointed out in the quoted article, a solution appears to exist for the case when $\bar{E} = 0, \bar{B} = 0$ and $\nabla \times \bar{A} = 0$ for a new wave satisfying

$$\bar{A} = \nabla S \text{ and } \phi = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{DS}{Dt}, \quad (9)$$

with S then satisfying

$$\nabla^2 S - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{D^2 S}{Dt^2} = 0. \quad (10)$$

These modified equations still assert that S is a potential with a wave equation – albeit a progressive wave equation – mathematically, which suggests the propagation of this wave even though $\bar{E} = \bar{B} = 0$ and the Poynting theorem implies no electromagnetic power flow. Note that, for convenience, the same notation for vectors has been adopted here as is used in the original quoted article.

A surprising situation arises where the \mathbf{E} field may assume a non-zero value. This follows because if only $\mathbf{B} = 0$, then $\nabla \times \mathbf{A} = 0$ still and this implies $\mathbf{A} = \nabla S$ as before. If this is substituted as previously then, provided the operator ∇ commutes with both ∇^2 and $\partial^2/\partial t^2$, the same wave equation for S emerges. It is this reasoning that allows scalar waves for a non-zero \mathbf{E} field. Hence, in the Maxwell electromagnetic equations, scalar waves are found after simply putting \mathbf{B} equal to zero - there being no need to have a zero \mathbf{E} field. It follows immediately that, in the gravitational situation, scalar waves appear regardless of whether there is a second field or not because to realise them you may simply assume the existence of such a field and then put it equal to zero!

Bearden informs us of important yet often neglected history in his volume, *Gravitobiology*, Cheniere Press, 1991, p. 72:

⁴ <https://www.cia.gov/library/readingroom/docs/CIA-RDP96-00792R000500240001-6.pdf>,

“The scalar component of Maxwell’s quaternions captured and retained the *internal vectors* that result from zero-vector summations of non-zero EM force fields. Oliver Heaviside (and to a lesser extent Willard Gibbs) discarded the entire internal EM vector region when he excised the scalar component of the quaternions. The internal EM vector region is the electro-gravitational region, and that is what was discarded — all those parts of Maxwell’s theory where EM forces turn to gravitational potential. Accordingly, Heaviside only captured a subset of Maxwell’s unified EM/G field theory; he captured only that small subset where gravitation and electromagnetism are mutually exclusive.” (Gravitobiology, Cheniere Press, 1991, p. 72)

These vital points should be noted carefully when considering the work of T. Brown below.

3. Theory from Brillouin, Carstoiu and Brown

For basic theory we may turn to work by Brillouin which introduces several key concepts that are directly utilized within practical applications. In a fine text by Brillouin, *Relativity Reexamined (1970)* [20], we see several basic ideas which prove out in applied practice and also, introduction to the work of Carstoiu⁵. This offers a reasonable approach to the similarities and eventual union of electrostatics and gravistatics.

From that text by Brillouin we read pp. 88-89:

Coulombs law for charges Q_1 and Q_2 dielectric power e is given by

$$\mathbf{f} = \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{e r^2} \mathbf{r}^0 \quad (11)$$

Newton’s law for masses M_1 and M_2 , Newton’s constant G is written

$$\mathbf{f} = -G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r^2} \mathbf{r}^0 \quad (12)$$

The notation \mathbf{r}^0 denotes a unit vector in the direction \mathbf{r} . These formulae are identical if

$$e = -1/G = -1.5 \times 10^7 \quad (13)$$

Hence, if the assumption made is valid, it follows that Newton's attraction corresponds to a *large negative dielectric constant*. That implies negative energy and hence, negative mass.

It is found that physics using materials with a very high specific inductive capacity or dielectric constant (K) provide the greatest anti-gravitational lofting. [14, 15].^Φ

According to Brillouin that high negative dielectric constant corresponds to a distribution of negative mass within the gravitational field (p. 93). We also learn a very important fact concerning electromagnetic fields and mass, that every mass M is surrounded by an atmosphere of “mass plasma” resulting from the energy densities in the field. (p. 90). Then, we also read that

“... a "mass plasma" would differ from an electric plasma; attractions and repulsions would not lead to the same type of mixtures in both cases.” (p. 90)

It is proposed that those *mass plasma densities* are associated with specific longitudinal expressions associated with electromagnetic expressions, meaning *the gravitational force carriers*, for those reasons stated below. Force carriers are virtual particles.

Within perturbation theory of quantum field theory we find *virtual particles*. They are a *transient fluctuation of some unknown sort*, limited by ‘uncertainty.’ They are ‘fluctuations of the underlying field’ and are *associated with particles*, to represent the reversed doctrine of modern causality (see previous text concerning fields and particles). In Wikipedia we read:

“Any process involving virtual particles admits a schematic representation known as a Feynman diagram⁶, in which virtual particles are represented by internal lines (...) The accuracy and use of virtual particles in calculations is firmly established, but as they cannot be detected in experiments, deciding how to describe them precisely is a topic of debate.”⁷

We state without the possibility of contradiction

^Φ The term *lofting* taken as defined in the document *Electrogravitics Systems*: "the action of lévitation where gravity's force is more than overcome by electrostatic or other propulsion." p. 52.

⁶ Creative Commons. (CC-BY 4.0). Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, Feb 2020. URL: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Feynman_diagram.

⁷ Creative Commons. (CC-BY 4.0). Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, Feb 2020. URL: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Virtual_particle.

⁵ See <http://viXra.org/abs/1701.0533>.

that *Virtual particles are not real objects. Virtual particles are abstract mathematical objects.* Some real object must be performing these functions. We propose that the impulse associated with a particle which interacts as a force carrier is the longitudinal condensational wave associated with transverse wave expressions, and, within gravitational dynamics that a longitudinal wave also acts, but in this case to polarize the nuclear gravitational attraction of massive bodies. There is a real object performing these physical operations but it has been missed as the equations and medium through which the wave travels have been incorrectly understood and, in the case of the needed solution to the equations of Maxwell, *the science has simply been suppressed.* "Virtual particles" within functional theory are longitudinal scalar waves bound to matter. [2]. With this in mind we reference the nonlinear equations for gravitation defining *negative* (dielectric) mass densities as derived by Brillouin, in explaining the science of Carstouiu, and that for related electromagnetism then specifying *both* positive and negative densities, as would indeed be associated with electromagnetic and gravitational fields. [21] (p. 102) **It is then deduced that those specified resulting mass-density distributions in an electromagnetic field will generate new gravitational fields.** (p. 103)

Using the same notation as that used above, rewriting the usual Maxwell electromagnetic equations for the gravitational case, Carstouiu obtains

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = -\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial t}, \quad (14)$$

$$\nabla \times \Omega = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}}{\partial t} - \frac{G}{c^2} \mathbf{J}_g, \quad (15)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F} = -G\rho_g, \quad (16)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \Omega = 0, \quad (17)$$

where ρ_g is the mass density, \mathbf{J}_g the gravitational current, and Ω , what Carstouiu refers to as the gravitational vortex.[†]

[†] Having introduced Carstouiu's basic ideas, Brillouin continues by noting that the energy density in the field yields what might be termed a new mass density equivalent which turns out to possess a negative sign. He goes on to point out that this extension to Carstouiu's work raises several questions such as,

What meaning does the gravitational vortex have and what role does it play?

It may now be seen that electromagnetic fields do in fact theoretically appear to present both positive and negative dielectric electrical and associated mass plasma densities, so it then seems gravitation should have within its field expressions a natural coupling to electromagnetic fields according to Brillouin, as he interprets the transverse gravitational wave theory of Carstouiu. If this interpretive theory of Brillouin's is correct, we should see real physical indications that negatively charged electron plasmas and their respective mass plasma components, and positively charged proton plasmas and their respective mass plasma components do couple to gravitational fields effectively under specific conditions. Functional military technology based in the patents of T. Brown [15], demonstrate exactly this predicted electromagnetic to gravitational field coupling effect.

Patent information from the work of T. Brown states, as referenced from the source document Electrogravitics Systems [15]:

"Such a machine has two major parts A and B. These parts may be composed of any material capable of being charged electrically. Mass A and mass B may be termed electrodes A and B respectively. Electrode A is charged negatively with respect to electrode B, or what is substantially the same, electrode B is charged positively with respect to electrode A, or what is usually the case, electrode A has an excess of electrons while electrode B has an

and

How and where might it be observed?

Further investigation is contained in Carstouiu's work but it is noted that the similarity between the above equations of Carstouiu and the more familiar Maxwell electromagnetic equations leads to further thoughts, possibly the most important being that, since both types of wave propagate with the same speed, the possibility of an intercoupling of the two is definitely raised. The electromagnetic energy density is seen to represent a positive mass density which should be added to the above mentioned negative energy density. The resulting mass-energy distribution in any electromagnetic field must then generate new gravitational fields. Hence, this little known investigation, brought to light by Brillouin, leads to an extremely clear indication of a simple coupling between electromagnetism and gravitation.

Please see further extensive insights below concerning proposed gravitational propagation speeds, em propagation speeds and gravitational-field to electromagnetic-field coupling.

excess of protons.

While charged in this manner the total force of A toward B is the sum of force g (due to the gravitational field), and force e (due to the imposed electrical field) and force x (due to the resultant of the unbalanced gravitational forces caused by the electro-negative charge or by the presence of an excess of electrons of electrode A and by the electro-positive charge or by the presence of an excess of protons on electrode B).

By the cancellation of similar and opposing forces and by the addition of similar and allied forces the two electrodes taken collectively possess a force $2x$ in the direction of B. This force $2x$, shared by both electrodes, exists as a tendency of these electrodes to move or accelerate in the direction of the force, that is, A toward B and B away from A. Moreover any machine or apparatus possessing electrodes A and B will exhibit such a lateral acceleration or motion if free to move." [15]

This same technology is now used in the B2 bomber which, just as in the work of Brown, places positive plasmas in front of the craft at the leading edges, and an atmosphere of negative plasmas is then added to the exhaust stream, in close imitation of the original work of Brown [15, 22]. Dielectrics act within electric fields to influence electric charges that alter their average equilibrium positions creating dielectric polarization, where positive charges are displaced in the direction of the field and negative charges are displaced in the opposite direction. The plasmas appear to be separated from source electromagnetic field expressions by the capacitor itself via dielectric polarization, then, the respective charged plasmas are shunted by wires to their various functional allocations [15].

It is now clear that positively charged and negatively charged plasmas do have functional and not just theoretical gravitational coupling effects.

Then, it is seen [15] that the B2 bomber can utilize the gravitational field it creates as the sole energy source to extract flight sustaining energies sans use of its engines to generate thrust; engines which when engaged do indeed also function to power Brown style power creating flame-jet generators. This actual applied avionic engineering is practical demonstration of the fact that gravitational expressions offer us a pathway

to clean and nearly limitless energies. In this mode of operation the B2 demonstrates an engineless capacity where jet propulsion and fuel consumption is nil, yet sustained flight is achieved and theoretically can be infinitely sustained. It is stated the plane is then capable of "perpetual propulsion", although care should be taken in interpreting statements such as this in light of restrictions imposed by the Laws of Thermodynamics as far as perpetual motion is concerned. Energy and its conversion to work extend from tapping the near limitless gravitational/aetheral energetic reservoir within the efficiencies of available technology.

"In such a "coasting mode," where jet combustion is entirely shut off, the B-2 would be able to fly for an indefinitely long period of time with essentially zero fuel consumption, powering itself primarily with energy tapped from its self-generated gravitational gradient. For example, during coasting, the kinetic energy of the scooped air stream would arise entirely from the craft's own forward motion, this motion, in turn, being due to the pull of the electrogravitic propulsion field. The kinetic energy of this ionized air stream is responsible for linearly accelerating negative ions down the B-2's exhaust ducts and hence for creating the multi-megavolt potential difference relative to the positively charged engine body. The craft's high-voltage electron collector grids (the overwing exhaust ducts) recover a portion of this power to run the craft's ionizers. Provided that this power drain is not excessive and that the plane's propulsive gravity field can be adequately maintained, the craft would be able to achieve a state of perpetual propulsion. Such perpetual motion behavior is possible in devices having the capability to manipulate their own gravity field." [15, p. 94.]

4. Here we see the gravitational mechanism related to the two electrical and mass plasmas

"Not only can a gravity field exist in the form of a matter-attracting gravity potential well, as standard physics teaches, but it can also exist in the form of a matter-repelling gravity potential hill. Moreover, it predicts that these gravity polarities should be directly matched with electrical polarity: positively charged particles such as protons generating gravity wells and negatively charged particles such as electrons generating gravity hills." (p. 82).

Theoretically we find within these explanations presented in [15], a possible explanation for the attractive effects of negative dielectric gravitational distributions: "Thus contrary to conventional theory, the electron produces a matter-repelling gravity field. Electrically neutral matter remains gravitationally attractive because the proton's G-well marginally dominates the electron's G-hill." (p. 82, footnote). *It appears that between the two dielectric forces, the residual is Newton's gravity.* So, we can see quite easily that: "Consequently, subquantum kinetics predicts that the negative ion cloud behind Brown's disc should form a matter-repelling gravity hill while the positive ion cloud ahead of the disc should form a matter-attracting gravity well." (p. 82) This appears to be exactly how Brown's flying discs, linear gravity engines (see below and above) and the B2 drive system works. As to secrecy, in Cook's *The Hunt for Zero Point*, [22] we read that Britain's most prominent aerospace journalist Bill Gunston says he has, "...no wish to reside in the tower [of London], so had refrained from discussing clever airplanes with leading edges charged to millions of volts positive and trailing edges to millions of volts negative." (p. 125)

Next, it is seen that patented designs which again use the ideas of Brown to gain a million over one efficiency, and are used to produce power.

"On the other hand the motors when capable of creating sufficient power to generate by any method whatsoever all the electrical energy required therein for the operation of said motors are distinguished by being internal or self-excited. Here, it will be understood that the energy created by the operation of the motor may at times be vastly in excess of the energy required to operate the motor. In some instances the ratio may be even as high as a million to one. (...) Furthermore, said acceleration in the self-excited gravitator motor can be harnessed mechanically so as to produce usable energy or power, said usable energy or power, as aforesaid, being derived from or transferred by the apparatus solely from the energy of gravitation." [15, p. 59]

5. Physical basis of gravitational and electromagnetic fields: the scalar potentials

What is the actual physical basis of gravitational fields and field effects associated with electromagnetism? Physics is often based on nonphysical mathematical abstractions. However,

quantum theory must have a physical basis for its postulated effects and, in the electromagnetic potentials themselves, we do indeed have an actual physical basis for observed field effects. Electromagnetic potentials even apart from external fields have physical reality and effects! [18]. "In other words, in a field-free multiply-connected region of space, the physical properties of the system still depend on the potentials." (p. 490) Those potentials are provably real, actual fundamental pieces of the physical system. Next, we see that the entire electromagnetic field structure and so that of the elementary electron particle itself, may be created entirely from the scalar potentials alone! [16]^Δ

Scalar waves are gravitational waves. [2] Such scalar waves are necessarily formed of the scalar potentials, which are in fact the electrical potentials of the energy density itself, or *aether* as it was once known. Gravitational fields and their expressions then, are electrical pressure expressions based in spin and charge cancelations across the wave as inductive electrics.[2] The gravitational field gains its physical reality in the same way the electromagnetic fields do: by way of the potentials which are their physical basis. The gravitational field itself then, is a derivative of the scalar potential field which is dynamically organized into wave expressions. Those gravitational expressions and their velocities being various, the speed of propagation depending upon the presence of mass leading to a moving wave medium and luminal velocities, or the absence of mass implying a stationary wave medium and resultant superluminal velocities. As both the electromagnetic and gravitational fields come of the same scalar potential field basis, it is not surprising that these two scalar derivative fields couple. We note that it appears the seemingly metaphysical notion of mass and hence physical-reality as attributed to inactive fields such as in that theory proposed by Maxwell, Faraday and Einstein could gain a physical basis and make touch with reality here in the demonstrated energetic physical presence of the

^Δ Recent analysis implies a slight correction to the paper [16] cited, see: *Hadronic Journal*, C. K. Whitney, Generalized functions in relativistic potential theory. vol 10, 1987, p. 289-290. and; T. Bearden, *Gravitobiology*, 1991, Cheniere press. p. 76. 4 such potentials are sometimes needed to replace classical EM with scalar interferometry in consideration of torquing in multi-bodied systems.

scalar potentials upon which field effects are factually based.

6. Gravitational and Electromagnetic Field Coupling.

Is there experimental evidence of gravitational electromagnetic field coupling leading to mass then behaving as a variable, via electromagnetic effects? Are there experiments demonstrating mass alteration under electromagnetic and or associated mechanical influences?

6.1. One can begin with evidence of mass alteration as demonstrated in simple experiments performed by Laithwaite. A steel gyroscope with no vanadium chrome or nickel to assure a *pure ferromagnetic material* of a considerable fifty pounds heft is spun up to speed. Although difficult to lift at rest, once spun up to rotational speeds with an electric motor the device seemed to lose weight and could be easily moved about with one hand as if it were quite light. Laithwaite was ostracized by academia for this new experimentally demonstrated knowledge. [23] However, the military was accepting of the ideas. Although Laithwaite's demonstration caused academia to reject him for his apparent violation of a sacrosanct law of Newtonian physics, NATO's *Advisory Group for Aerospace Research and Development* (AGARD) began a study to investigate, and in March of 1990 their report concluded that a "force generating" device such as Laithwaite's could if rightly applied counteract gravity. "Clearly, if such a counteracting force was of a sufficient magnitude it would propel the vehicle in a straight line in opposition to said field of force and would constitute an anti-gravity device." [22] (p. 83)

Although micromagnetic effects are omitted, we must begin by pointing out that within a Neo-Newtonian approach as specified within the essay *Mass Varies in High Rotation Even at non-Relativistic Velocities* found within the text *Neo-Newtonian Mechanics with Extension to Relativistic Velocities* [23] that mass does indeed vary in gyroscopic high rotation, as can be seen mathematically as well as experimentally.

However, it is proposed that just such magnetic effects as have been omitted from the

forementioned Neo-Newtonian and Newtonian analyses could be primary in creating these profound and observable effects which indicate the formation of an emergent predominant gravitational field emanating from the gyroscope, in predominance over the field effects and interactions with the earth's gravitation. Here the work of Carstoiu suggests to us that his gravitational vortex field Ω couples to the inductive B magnetic field of Maxwell in addition to those previously noted effects, so as to alter mass quite significantly, perhaps by way of inductively transferred angular momentum within dynamic vortical density expressions hence meeting those conditions of induction and momentum transference which are responsible for gravitational force, strength and directionality. In this way the angular momentum expressed within the induced gravitational vortex that is surrounding the gyroscope imparts the linear force expression observed.

6.2. Viktor Schaubberger had long ago created applied technology and various designs which used vortical theory to create self-sustaining gravitational lift and clean power generation. [22]. His theories are those of atmospheric implosion and vortical dynamics which in specifically designed rotating objects that influence both object charge and object induced pneumatic effects, foster self-sustaining extraction of gravitational energies and variable mass effects demonstrated as lofting. The device is spun up to between 15,000 and 20,000 RPM and becomes self-sustaining. We read, "...but having whipped the turbine up to around 15,000 to 20,000 RPM the motor was turned off and the operation became self-sustaining. By connecting the machine to a gear-shaft electricity could be generated from it; or if left to its own devices, it could be made to take off." [22] (p. 213)

Callum Coats offers theoretical explanation for the anti-gravitational effects. (ibid. p.221) High rotation speeds effect the atomic and subatomic aspects to create an anti-gravitational effect by way of alteration and extrusion of binding energies:

"A point is reached where a large number of electrons and protons of opposite charges and directions of spin are forced into collision and annihilate with one another. (...) At lower rather than higher orders of energy and the basic building blocks of atoms, they are

upwardly extruded as it were out of the physical into virtual states.”

Then further on:

“Through the interaction between centrifugal and centripetal forces functioning on the common axis, he was able to implosively return or re-transmute the physical form (water or air) into its primary energetic matrix—a non-spacial, 4th or 5th dimensional state, which has nothing to do with the three dimensions of physical existence.” In August 4th 1936, Schauberger himself writes- “I am now able to see that we can create anything we wish for ourselves out of 'nothing.' ” (p.221)

Therefore, one wonders how long the science which could save humanity and this earth has been suppressed?

then interpret the theories just espoused in some tangible, physical form. We have already noted that the gravitational field itself is based in the physical scalar potentials which are the energies creating electromagnetic field effects. These energies are “4th dimensional” as stated above, in that they move faster than c , and “5th dimensional” in that they move unnoticed through ordinary matter sans interactions, as a neutrino. These potentials and manifest scalar waves then, are the basis of “virtual” expressions in physics, as has been shown. Here is the basic synthetic and dynamic energy of the system itself, the identity of those “lower” order energies spoken of. Indeed, these energies are in fact the binding energies of subatomic neutron structure [2 and 6] and, as we have already seen, are also the presumed physical essence of the fundamental electron and proton. To annihilate electrons and protons is to release their formative scalar energies, those gravitational energies functioning as binding energies at close scales which held them together. We have shown the demonstrated *positive binding energies* of the neutron as they relate to scalar waves and longitudinal energies induced and the science of neutron transformations in detectors and matter formation theory⁶. [2]

One can then theorize, as to how the basic coupling mechanic would proceed to distort the gravity field to move objects and then interact

with the remaining gravitational system within celestial mechanics:

Recall the fact of mass densities associated with electromagnetic densities around charged objects and fields. Those mass densities and associated mass plasmas are of two charge types, positive and negative, with two energetic polarizations indicative of their inductive interactivities. (Brillouin, *Relativity Reexamined*, (1970) [21]). Mass densities/plasmas are defined then as the longitudinal component of the transverse electromagnetic wave triality, the force carriers, spin one photon perturbations, longitudinal particle associated electrical density born perturbations. The energy density (aether) then as you will recall has experimentally demonstrated physical potentials comprising the gravity field. Those potentials are then coupled to positive and negative electromagnetic transverse expressions, induced by the longitudinal component of transverse electromagnetic waves' triality to create one of their own of opposite spin, and together we have a “graviton” (induced scalar wave) emerge from the induced potentials and other joined electromagnetic longitudinal components, the appropriate spin induced across the wave [2] to then couple the electromagnetic to gravitation. The field variance density moves the craft as a function of the various inductive relations corresponding to attraction and repulsion resultant of the two polarizations associated with positive and negative mass plasmas.

Aether is often modeled as an incompressible fluid. In fluids that are incompressible, transverse waves do not propagate but under certain circumstances:

A liquid has no permanent rigidity and so can only transmit oscillatory disturbances in which the oscillations take place along the direction of propagation - i.e. longitudinal waves. In general, transverse waves, where the oscillations are perpendicular to the direction of propagation, cannot pass through a liquid without strong damping. There is support for the transmission of transverse waves under special conditions - e.g. if the medium is able to conduct electricity and if it is permeated by a magnetic field aligned in a special way.

The gravitational field is coupled to transverse electromagnetic wave forms moving at c , then propagating at super-luminal velocities as a longitudinal expression once away from mass,

⁶ Norman, Dunning-Davies (2017) Hadronic paradigm reassessed: neutroid and neutron synthesis from an arc of current in Hydrogen gas, *Hadronic Journal*. 40; 119 - 148.

again we state, *at super-luminal velocities* to maintain contact with celestial mechanics.

Two celestial bodies then, would interact gravitationally via electrical densities and associated mass density variances (longitudinal gravitation waves) in accord to those mass density and charge specifics set up around the object, to then spread out as circular/spherical waves emanating from the object at nonlocal speeds. Other gravitational bodies then, interact with just such longitudinal expressions of their own to form emergent lines of force (induced scalar waves) between those celestial objects *directly along the gravitational interaction axis*.

6.3. Next note the science of Sweet and Bearden which propose the extraction of energies directly from the energy density itself.

From Sweet and Bearden: “Utilizing Scalar Electromagnetics To Tap Vacuum Energy” [24]

“Based on E.T. Whittaker's previously unnoticed 1903-1904 papers which established a hidden bidirectional electromagnetic wave structure in a standing force field free scalar potential, a method of directly engineering the ambient potential of the vacuum has been developed and realized experimentally.

Adding Whittaker's engineerable hidden variable theory to classical electro-magnetics, quantum mechanics, and general relativity produces supersets of each discipline. These supersets are joined by the common Whittaker subset, producing a unified field theory that is engineerable and tested.

By treating the nucleus of the atom as a pumped phase conjugate mirror, several working model energy units have been produced which excite and organize the local vacuum, increase the local virtual photon flux between local vacuum and nucleus, establish coherent self-oscillations between the local excited vacuum and the affected nuclei, utilize the self-oscillating standing wave for self-pumping of the nuclei/mirrors, introduce a very tiny signal wave to the mirrors, and output into an external load circuit a powerful, amplified, time-reversed phase conjugate replica wave at 60 Hertz frequency and nominal 120 volt sine wave power.

Several models have been built, ranging from 6 watts early on to one of 5 kilowatts. Both closed battery-less systems with damped

positive feedback and open loop systems with battery-powered input have been successfully built. Open loop power gains of from 5×10^4 to 1.5×10^6 have been achieved.

Antigravity experiments have also been successfully conducted where the weight of the unit was reduced by 90% in controlled experiments, with a signal wave input of 175 microwatts and an output of 1 kilowatt.”⁸

6.4. Referring the reader to patents for working technology from T. Brown claiming a million to one efficiencies, **dated from 1928**. Again, one wonders how long the facts of gravitation and clean energy have actually been available to serve the beleaguered race of man?

6.5. Lastly, the reader is referred to new hadronic sources of energy which are free from pollution. See footnote ⁹

7. The Twin Paradox, a conditional resolution and absolute time

No discussion of gravitation would be complete without addressing the famous Twin Paradox of Einstein. Is the twin paradox made famous by Einstein real? It could be, or it could be an anomaly caused by the Lorentz transformation. Noting the well-known time difference between clocks on the space shuttle and those on Earth and other time dilation effects which although small were actually terrestrial, such as time differentiations between moving atomic clocks in airplanes and those on the ground it seems the paradox is actual. However, those experimental effects could be due to the Sagnac effect and accelerations caused by a curved trajectory. So, the question of validity of the paradox remains. If it is valid, how could it be accounted for? See *Relativity Reexamined* by Brillouin [21] for a statement of the basic problem.

Is there a physical reason for the twin paradox and a physical reason that a gravitational field would have any relation to time?

⁸ See also, *Foundations of Physics Letters*. Vol. 14. No.1. 2001. [25]

⁹ Norman, Dunning-Davies (2017) Hadronic paradigm reassessed: neutroid and neutron synthesis from an arc of current in Hydrogen gas, *Hadronic Journal*. 40; 119 - 148.

- a. The entire of space is filled with an electrical energy density (once called aether) which is the physical basis of the scalar potentials, and those are in turn the basis of field effects.
- b. This serves as a fixed frame of reference through which things travel.
- c. It has been experimentally demonstrated that effects occur upon physical systems through interactions with the potentials themselves. [18]
- d. As an object travels through the potential field ever faster, it traverses more potential interactions. Hence it travels at higher frequency than a slower object (that is less affected by a gravitational field).
- e. Higher frequencies represent less time per frequency cycle than lower frequencies and so, more cyclic/temporal density per fixed time unit at any relative higher frequency.
- f. Hence, the time difference in clocks between the twins is a function of the time difference of the two frequencies, one at a higher frequency relation to the potentials traversed, which are the aetherial/electrical substrate of travel for gravitational waves, and the basis of that field.
- g. We may then infer that the twins have in fact experienced *the same amount of temporal travel, one at fewer but more dense time units at higher frequency, one at less dense time units of greater number at lower frequency.*

It may be deduced from the above theoretical hypotheses independent of the validity of the twin paradox or its proposed solution that *absolute time corresponds to dynamic systemic interactions with the physical potentials as a standing reference frame with its mass equal to that of the universe.*

8. Conclusion

Gravitational theory holds within its correct understanding the solutions to the many problems of mankind, ranging from clean and abundant energies to the promise of space travel. Practical means and reliable engineering have long been applied to create the many technical solutions to the troubles of man, but, these answers have been

concealed from the public, business and academic science alike, in order to foster military supremacy and serve the secrecy in which it is based. Gravitation functions by way of longitudinal waves within the omnipresent medium of an energy density. These long utilized facts must begin to make their way into the public arena, that of business and academic science. This paper is intended to bring those vital specifics and practical notions forward so designs can be quickly created and used. It is our hope that the concealment of this science will end and the text we have written will serve to open those doorways so long left shut, and then allow the emergence of needed new advances which will serve our race.

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